

HYGIENIC ASPECTS OF SANITARY CLEANING OF RESIDENTIAL AREAS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17798523>

Overall, the increase in human waste leads to the following adverse effects: changes in the air quality; sharply increased pollution of open water bodies and groundwater; and severe surface contamination in populated areas. Given all this, cleaning populated areas of solid and liquid waste is a critical sanitary and hygienic task. Cleaning a populated area should be a unified system of measures covering the entire area. The processes of collecting, removing, cleaning the area, and rendering waste harmless should be mechanized to the maximum extent possible, and contact between the population and cleaning personnel and the waste should be eliminated or minimized whenever possible. Sanitary cleaning always consists of three stages: waste collection, storage, and removal to a disposal site. In our country, all this work is carried out by specialized organizations affiliated with municipal authorities (improvement trusts, housing and communal services, etc.). Sanitary organizations are responsible for verifying the proper treatment system and monitoring waste collection, storage, and disposal sites. When organizing solid municipal waste collection, it is important to understand its qualitative and quantitative composition. The qualitative composition of solid municipal waste (garbage) can be divided into its main components, the quantity of which determines the feasibility of recycling using various methods. These components include food waste, paper, and solid non-recyclable materials (coal, glass, and ash). For example, if we consider the waste generated by cities around the world, the highest concentrations of food waste (62%) are found in France, ash (57%) in England, and paper (65%) in Finland. The most important thing to understand about waste quality is its epidemiological significance. Solid municipal waste always contains a large number of microorganisms, which may include any pathogenic bacteria and viruses (gastrointestinal infections, helminthiasis, viral infections, zoonotic infections, etc.). A crucial aspect of waste collection is accurately determining its quantity. The number of waste containers required is calculated based on the volume of accumulated waste. The calculation is based on the annual waste accumulation rate per person, which is currently 1,000 liters. The volumetric weight of 1 m³ of waste is 0.2 tons, meaning 1 m³ of waste weighs 200 kg.

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